

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 4. Figure 4.5

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Description

Data were gathered from the IUCN website on global extinctions attributed to be caused by invasive alien species.

Process overview

1- All data were downloaded from the IUCN website (28 July 2021, IUCN Version 2021-1) of species that are EX (extinct) and EW (extinct in the wild) (assessments, taxonomy, and threats files).

2- We kept species with the category “8.1.1” and “8.1.2” cited as a threat (only considering invasive alien species and not native species)

```
EXIAStreat<-threats %>%  
  filter(threats$code == "8.1.1" | threats$code == "8.1.2")
```

and focus on species extinct when invasive alien species are cited as a threat for the majority of the range and inducing a significant decline.

```
EXIAStreatScope<-EXIAStreat %>%  
  filter(EXIAStreat$scope == "Whole (>90%)" | EXIAStreat$scope == "Majority (50-90%)")
```

```
EXIAStreatScopeSeverity<-EXIAStreatScope %>%  
  filter(EXIAStreatScope$severity == "Slow, Significant Declines" | EXIAStreatScope$severity == "Rapid Declines"  
    | EXIAStreatScope$severity == "Very Rapid Declines")
```

3- Then, we classified species based on their class to build a barplot for the number of EX-EW species by classes.

```
sp<-as.data.frame(unique(EXIAStreatScopeSeverity$scientificName))
```

```

colnames(sp)<- "scientificName"
IAS_EX<-inner_join(sp,taxa, by='scientificName')
EXAnimals<-IAS_EX %>%
  filter(IAS_EX$kingdomName == "ANIMALIA")
EXPlants<-IAS_EX %>%
  filter(IAS_EX$kingdomName == "PLANTAE")
Table1<-rbind(as.data.frame(table(EXAnimals$class)),as.data.frame(table(EXPlants$class)))
Table1$Freq<-as.numeric(Table1$Freq)
## Figure ##
p<-ggplot(data=filter(Table1,Freq>10), aes(x=reorder(Var1,-Freq),
      y=as.numeric(Freq), fill=Var1)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity", width = 0.8)+theme(legend.title = element_blank())
p + ylab("Number of EX-EW")+ xlab("Class")+theme_gray()

```

We also used the file “Assessment” downloaded on step 1 to obtain information about species last seen and create a barplot of the number of EX-EW species since 1500.

```

Last<-read.csv("DataLastSeen.csv", sep=";", header=TRUE)
Last$freq<-1

Date<-as.data.frame(Last %>%
  group_by(dataUpdate) %>%
  summarise(count = n()))

Date$dataUpdate<-as.numeric(Date$dataUpdate)
## Figure ##
p<-ggplot(data=Date, aes(x=dataUpdate, y=count)) +
  geom_bar(stat="identity", width = 1.5)+ xlim(1500,2050)
p + ylab("Number of EX-EW")+ xlab("Year")+ theme_minimal()+
  scale_y_continuous(
    labels = scales::number_format(accuracy = 1))

```

Protocol

Detailed description of the protocol

Data were extracted from the IUCN website (28 July 2021, IUCN Version 2021-1) of species that are EX (extinct) and EW (extinct in the wild) with the category “8.1” cited as a threat (only considering invasive alien species and not native species) and focus on species extinct when invasive alien species are cited as a threat for the majority of the range (scope >50%) and inducing a significant decline (“Slow, Significant Declines” “Rapid Declines”, “Very Rapid Declines”). Afterwards, the redlist package was used to extract more information about the identity of invasive alien species and their habitats.